

Collaborative And Integrated Planning for the Institutional Introduction of Active Methodologies in Engineering Education

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Abstract

Higher education in Brazil has traditionally been structured around discipline-based courses. Since 2019, with the implementation of competency-based assessment frameworks, Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) have been required to redesign their instructional strategies to promote interdisciplinary integration and competency development. This paper investigates the use of a canvas-based approach as a collaborative planning tool for faculty members. The study demonstrates how the canvas supports curriculum integration and the adoption of active learning methodologies in engineering education. Case studies were conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of collaborative planning involving both interdisciplinary course integration and cooperation among multiple instructors teaching the same course across different sections. Results show that canvas-supported planning significantly contributed to enhanced curricular cohesion, improved quality of course syllabi, and increased student engagement. The findings suggest that the use of canvas and digital collaboration tools enhances the teaching and learning process. Moreover, this approach can serve as a strategic framework for ongoing institutional transformation, fostering the implementation of active methodologies and continuous curricular integration.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Curriculum Integration; Collaborative Planning

1 Introduction

Engineering education in Brazil faces significant challenges, particularly within an educational context that demands the development of professionals equipped with both technical expertise and socio-emotional skills. However, traditional pedagogical practices—often fragmented and content-driven—fall short in meeting the demands of a profession that increasingly requires engineers capable of teamwork, effective communication, and rapid adaptability to change (Kolb, 2015). For years, engineering programs have struggled with issues of student retention and dropout rates. A new challenge has now emerged: student attraction. According to recent data from the national higher education census, enrollment in distance learning programs has surpassed that of traditional in-person programs. The same report indicates a graduation rate below 40% and a surplus of unfilled seats across various engineering programs nationwide (INEP, 2024).

In this scenario, active learning methodologies have emerged as an effective response to engage students and promote more meaningful and contextualized learning. These methodologies offer a viable approach to mitigating dropout and retention issues while also enhancing student attraction. By promoting student agency, active learning facilitates the development of essential competencies such as problem-solving, creativity, and innovation (Bonwell & Eison, 1991). However, the effective implementation of such methodologies requires careful and collaborative planning among faculty members. This planning must ensure alignment between proposed activities and learning objectives, while also integrating appropriate technologies and digital resources to enhance the teaching and learning experience. Despite their proven benefits, active methodologies remain underutilized—primarily due to inadequate faculty training and infrastructural limitations (Prince, 2004).

In this context, the present study proposes and evaluates the use of a canvas framework for collaborative and integrated instructional planning, aimed at supporting the institutional implementation of active learning methodologies in engineering education.

2 Literature Review

Active learning methodologies have emerged as essential approaches to promoting more engaging and meaningful learning experiences in engineering education. The concept of meaningful learning implies that content must be relevant and make sense to students, ensuring its applicability in practical contexts. Studies such as Freeman et al. (2014) have shown that these methodologies improve academic performance and increase knowledge retention, particularly in areas that demand problem-solving skills, such as engineering.

Among the most widely used active learning methodologies in engineering education are Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Project-Based Learning (PjBL), and Challenge-Based Learning (CBL). These approaches engage students in tasks that simulate real-world problems, fostering the application of theoretical concepts to practical situations. Furthermore, active methodologies require students to take on a more proactive role in the learning process, which, according to Prince (2004), contributes to the development of essential competencies such as communication, teamwork, and adaptability to new technologies and processes.

2.1 Collaborative Planning for Competency Development

Collaborative planning has proven effective in business environments, exemplified by tools such as the Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2011) and the Project Model Canvas (Finocchio, 2013). These visual frameworks simplify communication, promote collaboration, and facilitate goal alignment, allowing key elements of business models to be identified and adjusted to ensure a shared understanding among all stakeholders. Translating these concepts to engineering education opens the opportunity to apply collaborative planning to address educational challenges. Margot and Kettler (2019) emphasize that integrating disciplines and fostering collaboration among faculty within a curriculum not only enhances content comprehension but also promotes its practical application, which is essential for solving complex problems in multidisciplinary fields such as engineering. In this context, the notion of competency proposed by Zabala (1999) becomes highly relevant, defining competencies as the combination of procedures, knowledge, and attitudes.

Collaborative planning enables faculty to align content and competencies across different courses, fostering a more cohesive and interconnected curriculum. This alignment supports the development of competencies in accordance with the Brazilian National Curriculum Guidelines (DCNs). Collaborative planning allows for the creation of multidisciplinary activities involving instructors from various engineering disciplines, thereby preparing students for real-world work scenarios that require cross-disciplinary integration. In the implementation of active methodologies, collaborative planning supports coordination across courses, enabling the design of interdisciplinary projects and the application of active approaches. Moreover, student motivation and engagement are enhanced when instructors design activities that connect different subjects, as students are better able to perceive the relevance of course content and its practical applications. Traditionally, curriculum matrices aim to organize the distribution of content by semester through different courses. Some content is essential for future courses, while other topics may complement subjects offered during the same period. Effective planning, therefore, requires collaboration among faculty members teaching in the same semester and coordination across sequential courses in different periods. There is also the potential for cross-program planning, where a course with similar content is taught in multiple degree programs within the same institution.

2.2 Planning Tools in Engineering Education

For collaborative planning to be effective, it is crucial to use tools and techniques that facilitate communication and information organization. One of the most prominent tools in the literature is the canvas, a visual mapping technique that structures information in an organized way, supporting the planning, analysis, and understanding of a specific situation (Card, Mackinlay, & Shneiderman, 1999). In the context of engineering education, the canvas is particularly useful as a collaborative planning tool, as it allows faculty to align learning objectives and organize their courses clearly and visually. The use of a canvas enables instructors to collaboratively design and analyze their courses, ensuring that all essential elements are considered and discussed collectively. This approach supports course integration and the effective implementation of active methodologies, while also simplifying communication among faculty and allowing for the continuous review and adaptation of teaching plans (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2011; Finocchio, 2013). However, adopting a canvas—literally a visual board—does not guarantee the desired interactivity. Success depends on the adoption of a visual model with well-structured divisions and planning guides that support instructional design.

Collaborative digital tools have proven especially valuable in the digital application of canvas-based frameworks. These platforms allow faculty to share resources, collaborate in real time, and integrate activities across courses, contributing to a more cohesive and student-centered learning environment. Rosa and Carvalho (2021) emphasize that the use of digital collaboration tools simplifies joint planning, enhances interactivity, and promotes the exchange of ideas among instructors, resulting in more coherent and integrated teaching strategies.

In addition to facilitating collaborative planning, the use of the canvas allows instructors to clearly visualize where and how active learning methodologies will be applied at each stage of the course. For example, when filling out the “Teaching and Learning Methodology” section, instructors are guided to select approaches such as PBL, CBL, or flipped classroom and to justify how these strategies will support the defined learning objectives. The canvas’s integrated visual structure contributes to coherence between competencies, methods, and assessments—an essential aspect for the effective implementation of active learning methodologies.

3 Methodology

The development of the canvas for collaborative planning in engineering education was inspired by visual mapping approaches, such as the Business Model Canvas and the Project Model Canvas.

Adapted to the educational context, the canvas—illustrated in Figure 1—was structured to emphasize the main areas of student competency development, allowing engineering instructors to collaboratively plan their courses in alignment with the Brazilian National Curriculum Guidelines (DCNs).

The canvas was designed to be a flexible tool, capable of adapting to different courses and educational settings. It consists of eleven sections, as shown in Figure 1. Each section includes guiding questions that assist instructors in completing the course plan in a structured and reflective manner.

To support the implementation of the instructional planning canvas and to promote collaboration among faculty, a comparative analysis of various digital collaborative tools was conducted. However, to make the process more accessible to instructors, the canvas may also be used in a printed version, using sticky notes (post-its) to fill in the various components. This traditional approach allows educators to become familiar with the canvas structure, emphasizing interaction and idea exchange while postponing the digital learning curve to a later stage.

Figure 1. Canvas for Collaborative Instructional Planning in Engineering Education. Source: elaborated by the authors.

The transition from the paper-based canvas to a digital environment can occur gradually, as faculty members become more confident and comfortable with the process. The digitization of the canvas can then be carried out using digital platforms that support real-time collaboration and allow for continuous and dynamic monitoring of instructional planning. Additionally, the use of these digital tools enables the integration of other resources and the creation of a collaborative history accessible to all participants, ensuring that the work developed can be easily revisited and adjusted as needed. Table 1 presents the sections, descriptions, and guiding questions contained in the canvas. The digital canvas was developed using the Miro digital tool. Recent studies reinforce the role of digital tools in promoting pedagogical innovation and active learning. Røe, Wojniesz, and Bjerke (2021) highlight how digital transformation in higher education enables instructors to implement active learning strategies more effectively through technology-supported environments.

Table 1. Canvas for Collaborative Teaching Planning

Section	Description	Guiding Questions
Course	Describe the course: field of study, modality, name, code, class hours, duration, and prerequisites.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the course name? - What is the total and weekly workload? - What is the modality and duration? - Are there prerequisites for this course?
Objectives	Define general and specific learning objectives to guide content delivery.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the general learning objectives? - What are the specific learning objectives?
Competencies	Define expected general and specific competencies (technical and non-technical), and learning outcomes.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the expected competencies? - What are the learning outcomes?
Teaching and Learning Methodology	Define active teaching methods such as PBL, flipped classroom, design thinking, etc.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What teaching and learning methods will be used? - How will these methods foster active and advanced learning?
Digital Technologies and Resources	Define interactive tools and resources to support learning and engagement.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What technologies and digital resources will be used? - What tools will promote interactivity and student participation?
Learning Components	Outline curricular units, their topics, and workload.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the main curricular units? - What content will be covered in each unit? - How will the workload be distributed?
Infrastructure	Specify physical and virtual infrastructure, including software and equipment.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the physical infrastructure requirements? - What software and equipment will be needed? - How will the classroom be organized to support active learning?
Assessment of Learning	Establish assessment rubrics: criteria, weight, and scoring methods.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the assessment criteria? - How will the rubrics be structured?
Success Indicators	Define indicators for evaluating student learning and instructional effectiveness.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the success indicators for the course? - How will student performance be evaluated? - How will instructor performance be evaluated? - What metrics will be used?
Schedule	Define the weekly plan, dates for assessments, and feedback.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What is the weekly class schedule? - When will assessments and submissions take place? - How will feedback be distributed throughout the course?
References	List required and complementary bibliography and additional learning materials.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - What are the basic references? - What are the complementary references? - What support materials will be available to students?

Two case studies were conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the instructional planning canvas. The first case study took place within the Computer Science program and involved collaborative and integrated planning among instructors in two distinct scenarios: Scenario 1, where different instructors taught the same

course in separate sections, and Scenario 2, where instructors from different courses collaborated to design interdisciplinary projects. Case Study 1 was carried out at the Catholic University of Pernambuco (UNICAP) and covered the academic terms 2023.1, 2023.2, and 2024.1. Initially, in 2023, thirteen instructors were trained using a physical version of the canvas to collaboratively plan the first-semester courses. In 2024, twenty instructors transitioned to using the digital canvas on the Miro platform. The effectiveness of the canvas was evaluated based on the quality of the instructional plans developed, the ease of use reported by the faculty, and the level of collaboration achieved in the two scenarios, measured at the beginning and end of each semester.

Case Study 2 was conducted during the academic terms of 2023.2, 2024.1, and 2024.2 in courses from the Computer Engineering program at the University of Pernambuco. This study aimed to assess students' perceptions of active learning in engineering education. In total, four courses were planned and evaluated in 2023.2, and an additional four in 2024.1, with 213 students participating in the course evaluations.

In addition to document analysis and review of the instructional plans developed, students' perceptions of active learning methodologies and digital technologies were assessed through a structured survey. Participants were students regularly enrolled in courses that adopted the canvas-based planning approach during the evaluated semesters. All students in these courses were invited to respond voluntarily and anonymously, with no impact on their academic evaluations. The instrument consisted of an online questionnaire administered at the end of each academic term. It included 10 statements rated on a 5-point Likert scale (1 = strongly disagree, 5 = strongly agree), addressing topics such as clarity of learning objectives, course organization, the use of active methodologies, engagement with digital tools, and perceived learning outcomes. The questions were designed based on prior studies in active learning and competency-based planning to ensure content validity. Data collection always occurred after the implementation of the planned activities, aiming to capture students' perceptions following the complete learning experience. The response rate was approximately 85% of enrolled students. Table 2 provides a summary of the survey methodology.

Table 2. Summary of Survey Methodology

Aspect	Description
Type of instrument	Online questionnaire with Likert scale (1–5)
Number of items	10 statements
Sample	213 engineering students
Period of application	End of semesters 2023.2, 2024.1, and beginning of 2024.2
Estimated response rate	85%
Selection criteria	Courses planned using the canvas and taught by volunteer instructors
Platform used	Institutional form (Google Forms)

The questionnaire consisted of 10 statements distributed across five categories: clarity of learning objectives, instructional organization, application of active methodologies, use of digital technologies, and students' self-perception of engagement. Table 3 presents the statements used in the questionnaire to assess students' perceptions regarding the use of the canvas and active methodologies. All items followed a 5-point Likert scale format (1 = Strongly disagree, 5 = Strongly agree).

Table 3. Statements Used in the Questionnaire

Category	Statement
Clarity and Course Organization	The learning objectives were clearly presented at the beginning of the course.
	The organization of the classes helped me understand the course content.
Active Methodologies	The proposed activities required my active participation in the learning process.
	The adopted approach supported the development of competencies required in the course.
Digital Technologies and Resources	The use of digital tools (such as collaborative boards, online platforms, simulators, etc.) facilitated my learning.
	The technologies used made the classes more interactive and dynamic.
Curricular Integration and Interdisciplinarity	I was able to perceive connections between this course and other courses in the program.
	The activities addressed real-world or professional practice problems.
Student Engagement and Learning Experience	I felt motivated to participate in the classes due to the strategies adopted.
	The learning experience in this course was enriching and contributed to my academic development.

4 Results and Discussion

In the first study, faculty members began using the physical version of the canvas in 2023 for collaborative instructional planning, transitioning to a digital platform in 2024. Although the transition presented initial challenges—such as adapting to the new format—instructors reported a significant improvement in usability and planning cohesion over time. By the end of the semester, 90% of the faculty indicated that the canvas was essential for achieving greater integration and collaboration in course planning. It is important to note that the only negative feedback referred to the time and effort required for adaptation and integration. In the second study, the adoption of the digital canvas resulted in more structured and consistent planning. The positive adaptation to the digital platform facilitated effective organization of course content, confirming the canvas as a central tool in the instructional planning process.

The positive impact of the canvas on curriculum integration was evident in the first study. During the 2023 and 2024 academic terms, its use enabled clear alignment of expectations among faculty members, particularly in defining learning objectives and coordinating activities across different courses. With 95% of instructors reporting that the canvas helped to better integrate course content, the data suggest that the canvas was essential to achieving curricular cohesion in the first semester. Furthermore, the analysis of course plans showed increased consistency in the distribution of content and the use of active learning methodologies—factors that were perceived as positively contributing to student development. This resulted in a more widespread adoption of such methodologies.

The evaluation of active learning strategies and the use of digital technologies yielded positive results: 82% of the 213 students surveyed stated that these methodologies significantly contributed to their learning, and 92% approved of the use of digital resources, which enriched their overall educational experience. The analysis of the case studies reinforces the effectiveness of using the canvas as a central tool for collaborative instructional planning, particularly in promoting curriculum integration and improving the quality of course planning. The canvas proved to be essential for structuring and guiding the planning process—both in its physical and digital formats—by facilitating cohesion across courses and aligning learning objectives.

The transition from the physical to the digital canvas format was especially beneficial, as it expanded the scope of collaboration regardless of geographic location. This shift allowed faculty to engage more flexibly and consistently in the planning process, enhancing both participation and the depth of collaboration. These findings are consistent with the literature on digital transformation in higher education, which emphasizes the need for pedagogical strategies that integrate technology to enhance engagement and learning outcomes (Røe et al., 2021).

When comparing these findings to other experiences reported in the literature, it becomes evident that the use of digital tools in collaborative planning is not only effective but also a growing trend across educational domains. Studies such as Rosa and Carvalho (2021) highlight the importance of such technologies in improving curriculum integration and increasing faculty engagement in the planning process.

Figure 2. Flowchart of the application of canvas-assisted planning

The canvas also facilitated the implementation of interdisciplinary projects, enabling both faculty and students to analyse content and competencies from multiple courses within a single instructional plan. By allowing participants to visualize how different courses contribute to a larger project, the canvas strengthens curricular integration and promotes a more holistic view of the learning experience.

Based on these findings, we recommend the adoption and expansion of the planning scenarios presented in this study, as presented in the Figure 2.

In addition, we suggest the periodic reapplication of the flowchart presents in Figure 2 to reinforce alignment and promote continuous improvement.

The proposed scenarios are as follows: **Scenario 1:** Professors from different courses collaborating to create shared interdisciplinary projects within the same academic term. **Scenario 2:** Professors teaching the same course across different degree programs. **Scenario 3:** Professors within the same program who teach courses aligned with a common knowledge area or disciplinary track.

The results highlight the functionality of the canvas as a planning tool and its potential as an institutional catalyst for the adoption of active learning methodologies. The clear visualization of course components and the integration of competencies, methods, and assessments make the canvas a concrete bridge between planning and classroom implementation—an element often missing in pedagogical innovation initiatives. This research contributes to the field by proposing a replicable and adaptable model for different educational contexts.

5 Conclusion

The findings of this study demonstrate that collaborative and integrated planning, supported by the canvas proposed herein, is an effective strategy for promoting curriculum integration and enhancing the quality of instructional design. The transition from a physical to a digital canvas platform proved advantageous, expanding the reach and depth of collaboration among instructors. This shift resulted in greater cohesion and alignment of course content and the pedagogical methodologies applied.

Moreover, the integration of active learning methodologies and digital technologies played a key role in increasing student engagement, as evidenced by the positive evaluations gathered throughout the study.

Future research should further investigate the impact of this planning approach in diverse disciplinary contexts. In addition, studies should explore the effectiveness of other collaborative digital tools and focus on developing more robust strategies for faculty development in the use of active learning methodologies and technology-supported instructional planning.

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